

1 **COMT in human AD.**

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6 We recently utilized induced pluripotent stem cells from humans with a rare neurodegenerative disease
7 sharing disease pathology with that of humans with ALS and PD (expression of alpha syndrome nuclein
8 and TDP-43) to demonstrate that activation of a gene involved in dopamine metabolism, COMT, was
9 among those most differentially expressed transcriptome wide, activated to an extent far greater than most
10 any gene. The magnitude of COMT activation in iPS cells from patients with AD was similar to that of
11 patients with PD and patients with ALS.

12 We report here the discovery of COMT activation in Alzheimer's Disease, identified using brain tissues of
13 humans with Alzheimer's Disease.

14 We show here that in the human brain, when comparing the entorhinal cortex, the frontal cortex and the
15 temporal cortex, expression of COMT is highest in the entorhinal cortex, and that when studying gene
16 expression within each region of the brain, respectively, that COMT expression is highest earlier in
17 disease, or at Braak NFT stage 0, which we interpret to be earlier in disease rather than a less severe
18 disease. In each region, COMT expression was relatively higher at Braak stage 0 as compared to Braak
19 stage V-VI. These are post mortem samples.

20 Together, the data support a model wherein neurodegeneration resulting from very high levels of COMT
21 activation occurs early in disease, followed by further neurodegeneration and cognitive decline resulting
22 from or accompanied by presence of Tau neurofibrillary tangle.
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